

Effect of the force from fixed orthodontic appliance on the mandible. A part of the whole picture we need to comprehend

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Abstract

Orthodontic appliance when used apply a force, it will ultimately be transferred to the alveolar process which will cause a strain to the whole mandible not just the alveolar process. This strain will depend on the extent of the force delivered by the used device. Response is not involving the PD space only, but it extends to involve a wider region of the mandible. Just looking for the alveolar process without the whole mandible is a mere SILO THINKING. In this paper we want to explore the extent of orthodontic forces on the mandible emphasizing the importance of PD ligaments

Keywords: Bone, Biomechanics, orthodontic forces, teeth as jaws weakeners, stiffness of bone, jaws weakeners numerical simulation.

Introduction

We had published many papers on the effect of the teeth on the bone and vice versa. The orthodontic force will affect the alveolar process globally and locally. Teeth should be regarded as jaws weakeners (1). This concept should be a keystone in the biomechanics of the jaws.

In our previously published paper, we had demonstrated clearly the effect of the PD passively on the alveolar process. (2) In this paper we will demonstrate the effect of the next factors on the strain of the mandible:

- 1- absence of PD ligament on the orthodontically strained mandible
- 2- nature of the tooth and titanium dental implants and how this will affect the stress transfer from the tooth or implant to the alveolar bone.

The current concept should be coupled with the other model of the remodeled strained bone, (3) that we had been presented to understand the response of the response of the teeth to orthodontics force and relapse after the device removal.

Methods

We had built our mandibular model to be tested in all numerical models for the

- growth
- physiology
- effect of the implants and other surgical works
- trauma response
- base model for TMJ analysis

Figure 1 Every plan is start with a sketch. This is initial sketch of our model

Figure 2 The model was thickened by the size of 10mm

Figure 3 The model had been bended

Figure 4 Another view of the bended model. And More bending had been done

Figure 5 Submandibular fossa and more rounding was one to make more organic model. Closer resemblance to the real mandible had been gained

Figure 6 Future of the teeth socket

Figure 7 Socketed numerical model

Figure 8 We had mirrored that half to produce the complete mandible

Figure 9 This is the complete mandible with additional features to address many associated anatomical issues such as muscles attachment and TMJ capsules. Each of these structures will be explained in the context of the assigned biomechanical function. The next model is derived from this model to simulate the response of the mandible to the loads

Figure 10 We had applied fixed orthodontic device to the mandible. It had closed resemblance to the real variation. Further modification is needed and even this modification could be utilized to test additional models

Figure 11 The PD ligament had been modeled

Figure 12 This is the side of traction. It had been modeled as a screw

Figure 13 The other side the wire is fixed and the wire is free to move within the other brackets

Figure 14 In the current model the dotted regions are fixed

Results and discussions

In order to understand the effect of the occlusal force, we should study these conditions or at least considering them with all biomechanic analysis of the orthodontic force and correlate them with the continuous structure of the bone of the mandible. The maxilla had another story to be told due to its attachment at its base. Nevertheless the concepts in the current and previous paper are the same.

We have 3 factors that govern the response to the orthodontic force

- the occlusal force that will cause deformation of the jaw
- the passive presence of the orthodontic hardware will apply an effect on the jaws strain
- the activated orthodontic device will exert another strain on the jaw that should be calculated.

The application of the orthodontic force by the used hardware, specially fixed appliance, will direct the response of the PD ligaments strain toward the desired direction

Figure 15 The first figure on the left represents the application of only the occlusal force. The middle figure represents the application of the force on the posterior teeth. The figure on the right represents the application of the occlusal force on the anterior teeth and the application of simultaneous orthodontic force

Figure 16 This is the strain of the mandible without any orthodontic brackets. Only occlusal force on the anterior teeth

Figure 17 Strain with occlusal force on the anterior teeth and the orthodontic device is present passive without any application of any orthodontic force

Figure 18 This is the strain of the mandible with orthodontic brackets plus occlusal force on the anterior teeth

Figure 19 Strain energy density of the tested model. On the left only teeth and exposed to occlusal force anteriorly. Middle occlusal force anteriorly with passive presence of the orthodontic device without any activation. On the right the application of the orthodontic force in addition to the occlusal force application as well

Pattern of distribution is the most important issue to be noticed in all of the numerical studies

Figure 20 Strain energy density without orthodontic device and occlusal force on the anterior

Figure 21 Strain energy density with non-activated orthodontic device and occlusal force on the anterior

Figure 22 Strain energy density with activated orthodontic device and occlusal force on the anterior

Previous models is for the force applied on the anterior teeth

Next models for force applied over the posterior teeth

Figure 23 The force application site on the posterior teeth

Figure 24 These are the strain models of the force applied to the posterior teeth without any orthodontic force application device. First model showing the force application and the orange tooth had been regarded normal, next to it on the right is the freshly extracted, next to it is the consideration of a well osseointegrated implant made from titanium and the final model, first model on the right, ankylosed or unresorbed healed edentulous area as the material assigned to it in the last model as normal bone

Figure 25 Strain of the mandible with all normal teeth

Figure 26 Fresh extraction site ant to the post force

Figure 27 Single Implant ant to force application site

Figure 28 Ant to the force application site the tooth is ankylosed and it could be regarded as healed unresorbed edentulous area

Previous models for force applied over the posterior teeth

Next models for force applied over the posterior teeth (strain energy density) In all graphs the legend had been modified just to better demonstrate the effect of the stress distribution. All he condition are the same as the previous models

Figure 29 the strain energy density of only natural teeth model with the force applied on the posterior teeth

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Figure 30 The strain energy density with forces applied on the posterior teeth and a fresh extracted socket in an anterior region to the force application site

Figure 31 The response of the jaws with an implant in an anterior region to the force application site

Figure 32 In this condition, the model is with green color had been represented as ankylosed teeth

Figure 33 First model from the left is an anterior teeth model, next to the right is a freshly extracted tooth, next is the implant model and final model on the right is the ankylosed tooth

Previous models for force applied over the posterior teeth (strain energy density). In all graphs the legend had been modified just to better demonstrate the effect of the stress distribution

All the next models are without consideration of the PD and the teeth are ankylosed to the bone

Figure 34 Displacement distribution

Figure 35 Strain distribution

Figure 36 Another view of the mandible with the strain distribution is apparent

Figure 37 Strain energy density of the plastic PD space

**All the previous models are without consideration of the PD and the teeth are ankylosed to the bone
All the next models are with consideration of the PD and the teeth are ankylosed to the bone**

Figure 38 Displacement in the deformed and non-deformed graphs

Figure 39 Displacement in better large graph

Figure 40 Strain of the mandible. The alveolar process is a continuous entity with all of the mandible

Figure 41 Another view of the mandible with the strain distribution is apparent

Figure 42 Strain energy model of the PD ligament component

All the previous models are with consideration of the PD and the teeth are ankylated to the bone
Another iteration had been used to demonstrate the effect of adding occlusal force in addition to the orthodontic forces.

Figure 43 The configuration of the anteriorly applied force

Figure 44 Displacement deformation and legend should be modified to better convey the idea

Figure 45 we had modified the deformation of the graph

Figure 46 This is better configuration of the legend and deformation

Figure 47 This is the strain of the orthodontics force and the addition of the occlusal force to the anterior teeth

Figure 48 Another view of the strain

Figure 49 Strain energy of the orthodontic force and the occlusal force on the anterior teeth. All previous models are anterior teeth occlusal force and orthodontic force. We had changed the occlusal force form the anterior teeth to the posterior teeth

Figure 50 The site of the force application on the posterior teeth

Figure 51 The force application on the posterior teeth

Figure 52 Displacement of the posterior force in addition to the orthodontics force

Figure 53 Strain of the mandible resulted from orthodontic force accompanied with occlusal force on the posterior teeth

Figure 54 Other view of the strain of the occlusal force with the

Figure 55 Strain energy density of the occlusal force model on the posterior teeth and the orthodontic force

Conclusion

We had presented a numerical model to introduce the new concept to the orthodontic community to better understand the effect of orthodontic force on the whole mandible

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.